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Annotation: This article says that national and universal values are directly related to each other. They both affect each other, one is due to each other, one is content and essentially enriched. The goal of all nations, ethnic and aspirations is expressed the integrity, its aspirations. Also, universal values are deeply and wide and wide universal significance from national and regional values. Universal values are in line with the goals and aspirations of all nations, ethnic groups and peoples in the world. A series of universal values includes universal problems associated with the progress of human civilization. The most important of these are the universe of universe, ensuring the development of science, keeping peace, storage of nuclear weapons, prevention of nuclear security, prevention of various diseases, energy protection, energy sources, and food and includes problems related to the development of the global ocean.

Key words: Universal values are to provide all the nations, nations and peoples in the world, the elimination of public security, the protection of various diseases, energy protection, energy sources, energy sources, energy sources, energy sources, and global ocean resources

President Shavkhat Mirziyoyev .- "We cannot imagine all our interests from the heart of the country and mutual respect, love, and solidarity of our society. All this is our sacred duty of each of us to our priceless treasure and keeping it as an eye. It will be blessed where solidarity and solidarity. "[1].

It is difficult to imagine national values of each nation with its history, spirituality, culture, specific customs, traditions. "When calling value, we must serve the interests and goals of man, ethith and social groups, and evaluate and understand the blessings of nature, the benefits, incidents of the appreciated nature." [2].

Validity is the concept of universal, socio-moral, cultural and culture in reality". This, in turn, shows the importance of values. National values are the form of originality related to ethnic aspects and features of the importance of the nation. There is no nation of non-specific values in the world. For example, every nation, the original citizen of the people wants prosperous and prosperous people. It is known that this is the main goal of the idea of national independence. Therefore, national and spiritual universities make up the important land of civil society. [3].

Visits are one of the most important factors that demonstrate the past, present and future of each nation. Scientists will be conditional to a number of species such as national, religious, local, regional and universities.

National values are formed on local and religious values, and universal values are formed based on many national values and will continue to improve over cent centuries. However, in today's rapid globalization conditions, any nation, and the traditions, and immortal values of any nation, stands differently from other nations.

Naturally, priceless values of nationalities do not simply appear in a couple or decades. Because the tradition of any important rearing, clothing, daily lifestyle, requires the tradition of any important rather than an important role, the "thing everyday way of life, which is deeply planted in the hearts of the people. Over the years, a certain look, accustomed, concept, the experiments successfully pass, develop, develops, and take its place in the life of the people.

As the high beings of the times, the values became a great spiritual power that called people to peace, kindness, goodness, harmony. Such values in the daily life, culture and spiritual community of the nation, in the cultural dialogue, mutual cultural communication, reflected in each other, each of them. That is why the values of thinkers' values are mentently mentently mentently.

The development of society has not been narrated in human history. As a result of the approachful approach to the socio-historical events, national values are also improving. National values include language, customs, history, culture, history,

traditions, traditions, traditions, cultures, traditions, economic, socio-political life. That is why values reflect the spiritual image of the nations.

In particular, in the love of the people of our people - the memory of the memory of the ancestors, the memory of the ancestors, the guilty, honor, honoring ones, constantly unselfishly discriminatory respect and service to their parents, especially parents Not betraying the rights of orphans and Esdays, the wealth of the neighbors, and in any circumstances, too many human qualities, such as myself and agal, forms the basis of our national values.

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After gaining independence, our hardworking people began to be carried out by the historical memory of our people, ancient customs, traditions, values, bringing the sacred work to bringing the sacred cadtions. In this process, it was noteworthy that unique values of nations and ethnic groups live in the country will be developed without restoring, developing the language and values of the North population [4].

National values include language, customs, history, culture, traditions of each nation, especially:

The Arab National Cultural Center.

For centuries, the Arabs have lived in Uzbekistan as a single nation. In 1991, an Arabic national cultural center was established in the densely lives in Kashkadarya region, which has been working until today.

Today, the center operates to the Al-Arabiya Folklore ensemble executable Arabic songs and dance. The unique creativity and art of the ethnographic team, which have several winners of the Friendship and Culture of Friendship and Culture

of Uzbekistan - the Total House, is a public weddings. In the village and steel villages near the city of Cattle and Steels, including the Arab people, will hold meetings with the figures, science and cultural figures of the Arab people[5].

Turkish National Cultural Center.

The first historical ties between the Uzbek and Crimean Pope were mentioned in the second half of the 19th century, it is primarily related to the activities of the teacher, writer and publicist of the great reformist of his time. In 1944, the majority of the most deportarians deported in 1944 adopted the Uzbek people. In 1997, the Krimtattar National City City City Cultural Center was established in 1997 and in 1997 to preserve the mother tongue, traditions and traditions of the people who live away from the historical homeland, make the main goals of this center are marked.

Crimea has a tradition of visitors of the creative people of Crimea, including representatives of representatives of representatives in Uzbekistan to the Avdet National Cultural Center. In turn, activists of the center are actively involved in events in their historic Moderns, including the International Crimson Festival of the International Crimson Festival, including Bakhchisarai, and Ismail Hawsparrat [6].

Uzbekistan Turkish National Cultural Center.

The mass transmission of the Turks to Uzbekistan was 1944. The first Turkish National Cultural Center in the Republic was established in 1991 in Bukhara region, while the Turkish National Cultural Center "Ahisxa" Uzbekistan was established in 1997 in Tashkent. Currently, the structure of the center includes divisions in Bukhara and Samarkand regions. In the center of the center "Sevinch", "Ahisxpet", "Ahisxa", "Ahisxa", Miko Comedy, "Nazimmedia" such as "Sevithkha", "Nazimmedia" such as the center of the Turkish people, Miko Combine and Gunesh Polulis Tools Ensembles are organized. The center regularly organizes literary meetings, exhibitions of national costumes and national dishes. Activists of the center participate in various new projects in cooperation with other national cultural centers[7].

Kyrgyz National Cultural Center of Uzbekistan.

Uzbekistan has a population of about 300,000 Kyrgyz, which is about 300,000 Kyrgyz centers, are focused on the folklorology, the pearls of national and world culture, Uzbekistan, and the junior culture, Uzbekistan and Presentations of Kyrgyzstan and books will be held with prominent science and artists. National and religious holidays such as the Uzbek national holidays are similar and religious holidays such as national holidays are very interesting and colorful. Ancient tradition with the efforts of the center: Beshiktoy - Laying the baby, noon, dedicated to the child's first step and other public ceremonies. The days of independence of Uzbekistan and Kyrgyzstan are rightly celebrated as a bright demonstration of the friendship of Uzbek friendship.

Kyrgyz cultural centers pay special attention to the upbringing of a subduble generation. Today, there are 60 schools in Kyrgyzstan in Kyrgyzstan. With the preparation and publication of textbooks in Kyrgyz language, special edition of the publishing house "Uzbekistan" is engaged in special support. Teachers of Kyrgyz schools, including activists of the center, participate annually in the republican contest "Teacher" and will be awarded with prizes[8].

In conclusion, universal values is a strong factor that will pass from generation to generation to the generation of society and itself. These national values serve students to form a zeal education.

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